

Exchange Behaviour of Coen_3^{3+} on Synthetic Humic Acids

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The uptake of Coen_3^{3+} at a particular pH (7.5) by the synthetic humic acids, one [SyHA(A)] prepared from benzoquinone and ammonium chloride and [SyHA(B)] prepared from benzoquinone and casein, show almost a linear relationship till the major exchange sites available at this pH are saturated. The exchange reactions, however, at different pH values exhibit three distinct stages of interactions. The release isotherms with monovalent cations are more or less of Langmuir type for $\text{Coen}_3 - \text{SyHA(A)}$ system and S-shaped for $\text{Coen}_3 - \text{SyHA(B)}$ complex. With both the systems the orders of reactivities have been evaluated. By using Kielland's equation, the thermodynamic equilibrium constants and standard Gibbs free energy changes for exchange reactions involving bivalent cations in respect of $\text{Coen}_3 - \text{SyHA(A)}$ complex have been calculated. It is observed that the log of corrected selectivity coefficients or thermodynamic equilibrium constants when plotted against the hydrated ionic radii and the reciprocals of the Debye-Hückel parameter a° indicate that the relative affinities of the counter ions for exchanger substrates are much better correlated with a° rather than with ionic radii particularly for monovalent cations.

EXCHANGE reactions on natural humus by using different cations have been studied by some workers¹ including the present investigators^{2,3}. But much less is known about such reactions on synthetic or model humic acids. The present investigation incorporates the study on the uptake and release of Coen_3^{3+} on synthetic humic acids prepared from two different sources (i) *p*-benzoquinone and NH_4Cl , and (ii) *p*-benzoquinone and casein. The purpose of this study is to understand the physicochemical aspect of such exchange processes in the light of Pauley's⁴ and Kielland's⁵ concepts. Here, Coen_3^{3+} has been chosen because unlike the trivalent metal ions, e.g. Fe^{3+} , Al^{3+} etc. the above complex ion is much less prone to hydrolysis even at a high pH

Experimental

Based on the oxidative coupling of quinone, model humic acid⁶ SyHA(A) and SyHA(B) were synthesised from (i) *p*-benzoquinone and NH_4Cl , and (ii) *p*-benzoquinone and casein, respectively. The acids were purified by the same procedure as adopted with their natural counterparts²: The elemental analyses show that SyHA(A) (Found: C, 54.54; H, 3.08; N, 4.44%); SyHA(B) (Found: C, 57.45; H, 3.98; N, 3.88%).

Potentiometry, viscometry, polarography, ir and electronic spectroscopy methods were used to characterise SyHA(A) and SyHA(B).

The experimental procedures followed in the study of the uptake of Coen_3^{3+} by synthetic humic

acid systems at a particular pH as well as at different pH values and the release of Coen_3^{3+} from $\text{Coen}_3 - \text{synthetic humic acid complexes}$ by using different cations including the organic cations were the same as reported earlier². The Coen_3^{3+} contents were measured polarographically using a Radelkis OH-102 type polarograph. It may be pointed out that the Coen_3^{3+} -complexes of the acid systems were prepared as described earlier².

Results and Discussion

At a particular pH of 7.5, the uptake of Coen_3^{3+} by SyHA(A) (Fig. 1) and SyHA(B) (not shown) exhibits a linear relationship till the major exchange sites available are saturated. From the plateau of the isotherms the exchange capacities of SyHA(A) and SyHA(B) are found to be 275 and 340 m.e./100 g, respectively, which correspond with the values (261 and 331.0 m.e./100 g) for SyHA(A) and SyHA(B) respectively, obtained by potentiometric method with Ba(OH)_2 in presence of 0.5 M BaCl_2 .

The exchange pattern of Coen_3^{3+} on the synthetic acid systems (Fig. 1) at different pH values indicates three stages of interaction: (i) at lower pH (3.5–6.3 for SyHA(A) and 3.0–5.5 for SyHA(B)), (ii) at higher pH (6.3–7.2 for SyHA(A) and 5.5–7.2 for SyHA(B)) and (iii) at a still higher pH (7.2 onward for both the acids). It may be pointed out that in this respect two stages of interactions were found with the natural humic acids². In the present case, however, the third stage of interaction may be construed upon as representing the exchange

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processes involving very weakly acidic sites dissociable at considerably high pH.

Fig. 1. Exchange isotherm of $[\text{Coen}_s]^{3+}$ - SyHA(A).

It is observed from Figs. 2 and 3 that the release isotherms involving monovalent cations, except H, with Coen_s - SyHA(A) system are more or less of Langmuir type while those with Coen_s - SyHA(B) are S-shaped, the slope of the curve gradually increasing from a low value to a high value. It is noticeable that for both the systems the reversal of exchangeability for Li and Na takes place at a lower concentration. Though H has displayed much higher exchangeability than other counter

Fig. 2. Release of $[\text{Coen}_s]^{3+}$ from Coen_s - SyHA(A) by monovalent cations.

Fig. 3. Release of $[\text{Coen}_s]^{3+}$ from Coen_s - SyHA(B) by monovalent cations.

ions, the maximum amounts of Coen_s^{3+} dislodged by this particular ion from Coen_s - SyHA(A) and Coen_s - SyHA(B) are only 18.7 and 15.3% as against 64 and 72% from soil and peat humic acids² respectively, under comparable conditions. It seems to suggest strong bonding of the Coen_s^{3+} ions with these synthetic humic acids compared to natural humic acids. The release isotherms with bivalent and organic cations for Coen_s - SyHA(A) are depicted in Figs. 4 and 5.

Fig. 4. Release of $[\text{Coen}_s]^{3+}$ from Coen_s - SyHA(A) by bivalent cations.

Fig. 5. Release of $[\text{Coen}_3]^+$ from Coen_3 -SyHA(A) by organic cations.

The corrected selectivity coefficients (K_e) and distribution coefficients (Table 1), computed in the same procedure as applied to the corresponding complexes of natural humic acids², indicate the following orders of reactivity for the acid systems, $\text{Li} \geq \text{Na} < \text{K} < \text{Rb} < \text{C}_s < \text{H}$, $\text{Mg} < \text{Ca} < \text{Sr} < \text{Ba}$ and $(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N} < (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{N}$.

TABLE 1 - DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS AND CORRECTED SELECTIVITY COEFFICIENTS FOR DIFFERENT EXCHANGE REACTIONS WITH Coen_3 -SyHA(A) AND Coen_3 -SyHA(B)

Electrolyte added	Electrolyte concn (%)	Distribution coefficient	Corr. selectivity coefficient
Coen_3-SyHA(A) system			
LiCl	3.0×10^{-1}	16.08	5.02×10^{-4}
NaCl	3.0×10^{-1}	12.86	6.9×10^{-4}
KCl	3.0×10^{-1}	11.47	8.25×10^{-4}
RbCl	3.0×10^{-1}	10.96	9.17×10^{-4}
CsCl	3.0×10^{-1}	8.82	11.92×10^{-4}
MgCl ₂	3.28×10^{-2}	20.99	2.36×10^{-3}
CaCl ₂	3.6×10^{-2}	15.14	3.22×10^{-3}
SrCl ₂	2.9×10^{-2}	14.59	3.47×10^{-3}
BaCl ₂	3.0×10^{-2}	11.86	3.80×10^{-3}
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NCl}$	3.1×10^{-2}	11.11	4.49×10^{-4}
$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NCl}$	3.3×10^{-2}	8.82	5.58×10^{-4}
Coen_3-SyHA(B) system			
LiCl	2.84×10^{-1}	41.21	1.78×10^{-4}
NaCl	3.0×10^{-1}	41.21	1.77×10^{-4}
KCl	3.0×10^{-1}	25.28	3.41×10^{-4}
RbCl	3.0×10^{-1}	21.47	4.3×10^{-4}
CsCl	3.0×10^{-1}	15.78	6.48×10^{-4}
MgCl ₂	3.4×10^{-2}	26.80	2.02×10^{-3}
CaCl ₂	3.0×10^{-2}	25.28	2.26×10^{-3}
SrCl ₂	2.9×10^{-2}	25.28	2.37×10^{-3}
BaCl ₂	2.94×10^{-2}	22.25	2.57×10^{-3}
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NCl}$	3.0×10^{-2}	23.44	1.98×10^{-4}
$(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4\text{NCl}$	2.5×10^{-2}	8.95	8.20×10^{-4}

Based on Kielland's equation, the thermodynamic equilibrium constants (K) for exchange reactions involving bivalent metal ions with SyHA(A)

systems have been computed. The standard Gibbs energy changes (ΔG°) for the reactions are also calculated by using the relation, $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K$ (Table 2).

TABLE 2 - THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES EVALUATED FROM KIELLAND'S EQUATION AT 25° FOR EXCHANGE REACTIONS WITH Coen_3 -SyHA (A) SYSTEM

Exchange system	Equilibrium constant (K)	ΔG° cal mol ⁻¹
$K_{\text{Co}^{2+} \text{Coen}_3}^{\text{Mg}}$	4.07×10^{-2}	1907.6
$K_{\text{Co}^{2+} \text{Coen}_3}^{\text{Ca}}$	4.90×10^{-2}	1797.8
$K_{\text{Co}^{2+} \text{Coen}_3}^{\text{Sr}}$	5.01×10^{-2}	1784.04
$K_{\text{Co}^{2+} \text{Coen}_3}^{\text{Ba}}$	5.56×10^{-2}	1722.3

For monovalent cations, the distinct non-linearity of $\log K_e$ vs hydrated ionic radii plot vis-a-vis nearly perfect linearity of $\log K_e$ vs $1/a^\circ$ curve (Fig. 6) clearly suggests that $\log K_e$ values are better correlated with $1/a^\circ$ than with hydrated ionic radii. It strongly corroborates Pauley's concept that the electrostatic attraction operative between the exchanger ions and the fixed ionic groups is an important factor deserving consideration in the ion-exchange processes. However, for bivalent cations, a close scrutiny of the curves in Fig. 7 seems to point out that the correlation between $\log K$ values and the reciprocals of Debye-Hückel parameter a° is only marginally better than that between $\log K$ values and hydrated ionic radii. This may be due to the fact that the bonding energy of these divalent cations compared to monovalent ones is more capable of off-setting the electrostatic attraction as envisaged in Pauley's concept.

Fig. 6. Correlation between corrected selectivity coefficient (K_e) and (i) hydrated ionic radii and (ii) Debye-Hückel parameter (a°) in the exchange of Coen_3^{2+} from Coen_3 -SyHA(A) by monovalent cations at 0.7 M electrolyte concentrations.

Fig 7. Correlation between thermodynamic equilibrium constants (K) and (i) hydrated ionic radii and (ii) Debye-Huckel parameter (a°) in the exchange of Coen_2^{2+} from Coen_2 -SyHA(A) by bivalent cations

It may be noted here that in most cases the curves relating to SyHA(B) have been omitted because they are more or less similar in nature to those obtained with SyHA(A) system

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